

THE SEMANTIC FEATURES OF IDIOMS DENOTING COLORS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotation. The article reflects that color is vital part of whole information. Colors shows meanings through linguistic symbols by mirroring everything which could be visualized. Ancient literatures highlighted color projection as an essential part of life. Colors exercise deeper effect on reactions and feelings of human beings. Mood is generally incorporations of such several constantly changing emotions which are quite often expressed in the form of language and gestures.⁹⁸

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Introduction. Color idioms are used in different languages to express feelings or to symbolize cultural meaning. In translation, the issue of no equivalence emerges when translating color idioms since they carry cultural specific connotations. Idioms are generally associated with their original culture, and as a result, this association increases significantly with color idioms. Therefore, translating color idioms from one language to another might be daunting task due to cultural gaps which is caused by the lack of equivalence between the two cultures.⁹⁹

✓ The Semantic Features of Idioms Containing word “Black”

Black color is not used to convey positive meanings : *as black as night, be (as) black as a dog's guts*. Most of the phrases in the group are associated with disapproval (black sheep of the family, black look), sadness and gloom (black mood, *be in a black cloud*), illegality (*black money, blackmail*) and evil (*(as) black as the devil, black as hell*).

✓ The Semantic Features of Idioms Containing word “white” Contrary to black, white usually has positive connotations. Ex: *white sheep*
One who is dutiful and obedient, the opposite of a rebellious "black sheep.

“Everyone likes me because I'm the white sheep of the family. The same cannot be said for my wild cousin Nathan!”¹⁰⁰

white as snow means Extremely white or pale in color or complexion.

Now that my grandfather has stopped dying his hair, it's become as white as snow. My father, his face white as snow, put the phone down and told us he'd lost his job.

✓ The Semantic Features of Idioms Containing word “Red”

express feeling or expression of intense embarrassment or deep embarrassment are *a red face and to be red*

He's going to have a red face once he realizes that the mechanic he yelled at the phone wasn't the one who worked on his car.

Red with anger or the face associated by means of anger. *Red-handed* In the act of doing something, especially something illegal or nefarious. The phrase might have originally referred to blood on a murderer's hands.

✓ The Semantic Features of Idioms Containing word “Green” It is also the signal of safe. *Green As Grass* used to describe something that is very green in color. popular idiom “*give (someone) the green light*”, the speaker aim to give the hearer a permission/ promise to do something. Usage of idioms for very young and/or inexperienced person : *To be green as a Gooseberry*, Anyway, the idioms which comprehend the word green is sometimes indicate, jealousy, anger and envy. Example for them “*green with envy*” and *the “green-eyed monster”*.

✓ The Semantic Features of Idioms Containing word “Blue”

⁹⁸https://www.researchgate.net/publication/285055961_A_PsychoLinguistic_Exploration_of_Color_Semantics

⁹⁹ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280597546_Translation_of_Cultural_Bound_Color_Based_Idioms_A_Case_Study_of_Jordanian_BA_English_Students

¹⁰⁰ <https://idioms.thefreedictionary.com/white+sheep>>white sheep

Negative connotations such as to be hurt either physically or emotionally have also been associated with blue color *Black And Blue*, if something happened unexpectedly, suddenly use of “A bolt out of blue” idiom, “True blue” means loyal and faithful person.

✓ The color pink is associated with youth and femininity. *In the pink* and *in the pink of health* means good health, good condition, physically and emotionally¹⁰¹. *Tickled pink* very amused or entertained.

✓ The Semantic Features of Idioms Containing word “Yellow”
People are said to “*have a yellow streak*”. The idiom “*yellow-bellied*” in the sentence: “The man is yellow-bellied and is never willing to fight for what is right” also shares the same meaning to name a man with timid and coward characteristics.

✓ The Semantic Features of Idioms Containing word “Gray/ grey”
The idiom “*gray matter*”, where the colour may be accredited simply to the colour of neurons and brain in general, the terminologies in this group suggest that the situation or entity that they connote is somewhat shady, illegal or immoral. Grey matter here 12 means brain or intelligent. “Grey area” is a condition, where the rules are unclear and it is difficult or impossible to say what is right and what is wrong.

✓ The Semantic Features of Idioms Containing Words Denoting Color in Uzbek . “Black” is the colour of mourning whereas this color represents for something unlucky in English phraseology. In Uzbek *Qora qalb* refers to bad and envy person, *Qora niyat* means bad wish. *Qora bet* – a disgraced person

Therefore, there are many Uzbek idioms containing “white” with positive meaning: “*Oq yo'l*,” *Manglayi oq*”. *Oq yuzlik* means beauty. *Oq ko'ngil*-benevolent sympathetic person. Milk-white –*sutdek oppoq*.

The Semantic Features of Idioms Containing word “Red” It is the color of heart, passion, love and beauty and also anger. We can see this in some phrases popularly used by Uzbek people such as *A red face- olmadek qizil yuz*,

In addition, when we want to express somebody who does something wrong, we often use the color red to describe his face. So there is such idiom “become red-faced” in English and “*Qizarib ketmoq*” in Uzbek¹⁰²

The Pragmatic Features of Idioms Containing word “Blue” This is the color of sadness and depression: - “After seeing the old house in such bad shape, I had the blues for weeks” or “Patricia tends to feel blue around the holidays”¹⁰³

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES IN TERM OF SEMANTIC AND PRAGMATIC IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK IDIOM CONTAINING WORD DENOTING COLOR

Although Uzbek and England do not have the same derivation, it is amazing that both languages use certain accustomed images, daily events and phenomena to express the abstract sense recognitions to the means of metaphor, simile... Furthermore, Uzbek and English idioms comprehending words denoting colors share some of the same semantic fields such as human personality, human actions/activities, human psychological state, physical state, work. English and Uzbek differs from each other despite of having so many things in common. In attempt to collect and process the data, the author came to a conclusion that culture is the main factor influencing on the way of using color in idiom of both language, and it also the main reason causing the semantic gap in context.

Conclusion. In the comprehension of idioms that contain color words, there are resemblances among different nations. But differences still exist due to the unlike cultural traditions, history, seeing things. Therefore, it is important for language learners to make clear the

¹⁰¹ <https://blog.abaenglish.com/idioms-with-purple-and-pink/>

¹⁰² Subanova D.V. Translation of idioms in English and Uzbek. Article/Spirit Time. Berlin. 2018

¹⁰³ Liu D translation and Culture : Translating Idioms between English and Chinese from Cultural Perspective 11/2:2357-2362. 2012

semantic and pragmatic reflections of such similarities and differences, which can intensify their understanding of the two languages, thus a more effective intercultural communication can be realized. Semantic and pragmatic knowledge of comprehending and using idioms containing words denoting colors effectively. It can help the learners master the different elements in function and distinctive features of such these kinds of idioms in order to contribute to communicative ability efficiently and value the beauty of language with its diversity and variety.

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